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HOW DATA SECURITY & INTEGRITY IS ACHIEVED BY USING EXACT-CODING SCHEME OF CLOUD STORAGE IN CLOUD COMPUTING

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Abstract:

Cloud computing calculative is phenomenon which enable to access resources such as softwares, hardwares, and services over the global network. The main aim of user to store data on cloud to get security and integrity of data. Here the aim of this paper to ensuring the problem of data integrity & data security while keeping in cloud computing. TPA(Third Party Auditor) is used to expose different risks of cloud services to provide the benefit to the cloud client. For the data security, we proposed a correcting code for the distribution of file for data dependability. After using homomorphic token with distributed verification of correcting coded data, This approach achieve storage correctness and error localization. The security analysis shows the proposed approach is highly efficient and beneficial against malicious data alternation attack and server colluding attacks.

Keywords: Cloud computing, Data integrity & Security, Third Party Auditor.

INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing calculative phenomenon which enable to access resources such as softwares, hardwares, and services over the global network. There are sever approaches which open up the new era of cloud computing technology. Conceptually, users have computing platform from clouds to run their different applications. The more powerful processors together with the SaS(software-as-a-service) computing architecture leads to transform data centers into computing service on large scale. Now users can subscribe different cloud services because of providing very high and flexible bandwidth to the network. Cloud delivery models provide great convenience to users

while transforming data onto cloud due to lack of carefulness about complexities of service management.

We have live example of Amazon Elastic computer cloud(EC2)[3]. While this is online Internet based services that provide very huge amount of storage space with customized computing resources. This Information Technology infrastructure is eliminating the responsibility of local workstation data in cloud computing vendors and provide maintenance timely along with the result of data availability and data integrity for the cloud vendors[6]. Data integrity may be defined as accuracy and consistency of data storage that is indicated by modification between two updation of the data records. To ensure cloud data storage the cloud clients must store their information in the cloud and has no longer possess the data locally in cloud storage system[10]. The importance of ensuring the remote data integrity[3]. These concepts are not having to address all level of data security threats while client possessing on cloud storage because of they are focusing

on only individual's server and most of them not consider about dynamic data operations. That is the to choose homomorphic token properties to address these types of problems. which can be perfectly integrated with the verification of erasure coded data in cloud[11]. In Section II, system model and adversary model are described in background , related work is described in section III and in section IV Proposed system presented and conclusion is shown in section V.

II. BACKGROUND

We use two types of model e.g system model and adversary model in this paper regarding problem statement to get efficient support.

System Model:

In this model shows representative network architecture of cloud services architecture. This is shown in Fig 1. In that there are three network entities are as follows:

- User: User stores their data onto the cloud and relies for data storage and also for computation task.

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- Cloud Server: It is managed by the cloud service provider (CSP) to provide data storage computation resource with significant storage space.
- TPA: Third Party Auditor who is trusted and exposes risk of cloud storage services on behalf of cloud client's upon request.

There are following four cloud storages as below. In the cloud storage architecture, cloud make possible to access information from anywhere at any time.

Public cloud storage: In this type storage, it can be accessed by any subscriber with having Internet connection and can access to the cloud storage space.

Private cloud storage: In this type cloud storage, A particular or specific organizations have permission to access to those storage.

Hybrid cloud storage: Hybrid means combination of two or more characteristics. Here Hybrid cloud storage refers to the merging concepts of private and public cloud storage. In this critical data are located

in private cloud and other data is stored in public cloud and accessed from same.

Whenever the cloud client wants to store their data in cloud data storage via a cloud service provider into a set of cloud servers, which occurring at the same time and running in cooperated manner. Redundancy of data can be employed with technique of correcting code to further tolerate faults or server crash as user's data grows in size. In this paper, this dynamic features makes also traditional integrity insurance techniques useless and requires new solutions [8].Therefore, The correctness of data storage assurance will be of most necessary in achieving a strong and safely cloud data storage system in the real world [7]. In other words, we can say the clouds data are assumed by us are unexpected to be rapidly changing in a relative short duration. In this system, the main thing is that model shows point to point communication between cloud service provider and cloud client.

Adversary Model

The main concept of this model is to capture all kinds of data integrity threats. This cloud data is not indicated at client side but at the cloud service provider domain address. There are mainly two attacks from where this can come are as:

- External Attack: In the Attack, CSP (Cloud Service Provider) cannot be trusted.
- Internal Attack: This attack always comes from outside and who are beyond the control domain of CSP (Cloud Service Provider).

III. RELATED WORK

The importance of ensuring the remote data integrity has been highlighted by the following research. Works under different security models. And these can be useful to ensure the storage correctness without having users possessing local data are all focusing on single server scenario [1]. Provable data possession model for ensuring possession of file on untrusted storages [9]. Although direct applying these techniques to multiple servers could be

straightforward; the resulted verification would be linear to the number of servers. Jules et al.[5] defined a formal “proof of retrievability”(POR) model for ensuring the remote data integrity, their scheme combines spot-checking as well as error correcting code to ensure both possession and getting of files on archive service systems.

Bowers et al.[4] extended “proof of retrievability”(POR) model to distributed systems, all these schemes are focusing on static data. The effectiveness of their scheme rests mainly on the proposing steps that the user conducts before outsourcing the data file. Any change to the contents of data file, even few bits must propagate through the error-correcting code and the corresponding random shuffling process, thus Introducing significant computation and communication complexity; however the token pre-computation of the tags imposes heavy computation overhead that can be expensive for a whole file.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In this paper, it focuses on cloud data storage security, which has always been an

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most aspect of quality of service. For ensuring the correctness of cloud clients data in the cloud, in this paper propose a highly effective and flexible distributed scheme with two features, apposing to its predecessors. By using the homomorphic token with distributed verification of erasure coded data. In This paper proposed the integration of storage correctness insurance and data error localization most of works, the new scheme further supports secure and efficient dynamic operation on data block including operations. We relies on exact-correcting code in the file distribution preparation to support redundancy parity vectors for verification of erasure coded data using the homomorphic token, In this paper our scheme achieves the integration of data error localization and storage correctness insurance. This paper proposed highly effective and flexible distributed scheme with explicit dynamic data provide to ensuring the correctness of user's data in the cloud. our scheme enable the data owner to delegate of data file re-encryption and user secret key update to cloud servers without

disclosing data contents .In this paper we achieves this goal by exploiting and uniquely combing techniques that is token Pre_computation, error correctness verification as well as error localization and error recovery.

In the first reason cryptography services for the intention of data security protection could not be directly adopted due to the users" loss control of data under cloud computing. So, verification of correct data storage in the must be conducted without explicit knowledge of the entire data. Assuming various kinds of data for every cloud client stored in the cloud and requirements of long term continuous assurance of their data safely, the problem is that verifying exactness of data storage in the cloud becomes even more challenging. This construction drastically decreasing the communication and storage overhead as compared to the based file of replication in distribution techniques. Therefore correctness of data and availability of the data being stored on the distributed cloud servers may be guaranteed. The key issues

are to highly detect any unauthorized data alternation and corruption, possibly due to server compromise byzantine failure.

The token computation function we are considering belongs to a family of universal hash function, chosen to storage the homomorphic property. Which can be completely integrated with the verification of erasure-coded data? Then, it is shown how to derive a challenge-response protocol for verifying the storage correctness as well as identifying misbehaving servers. Finally the process for file recovery and error resurgence based on removal- correcting code is also outlined. It is well known that erasure-correcting code may be used to stand multiple failures in distributed storage space systems. In cloud data storage, we relies on this technique to dissolve the data file F redundantly across a set of $n = m + k$ distributed servers.

Notation and Preliminaries

d - The data file to be stored. We consider that F can be denote as a matrix of m equal-sized data vectors, each and every consisting of l blocks. Data blocks are all represent as

elements in Galois Field $GF(2^p)$ for $p =$ Eight or Sixteen.

- A : The dispersal matrix used for Reed-Solomon coding.
- G : The encoded file matrix, which includes a set of $n = m + k$ vectors, each consisting of l blocks.
- $d_{key}(\bullet)$ - pseudorandom function (PRF), which is defined as $d : \{0, 1\}^* \times key \rightarrow GF(2^p)$.
- $\phi_{key}(\bullet)$ - pseudorandom permutation (PRP), which is defined as $\phi : \{0, 1\}^{\log_2(\ell)} \times key \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^{\log_2(\ell)}$.
- ver - a version number bound with the index for single blocks, which records the times the block has been changed Initially we consider ver is 0 for all data blocks.

Let $\mathbf{F} = (F_1, F_2, \dots, F_m)$ and $F_i = (d_{1i}, d_{2i}, \dots, d_{li})^T$ ($i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$). Here T (shorthand for transpose) denotes that each F_i is represented as a column vector, and data vector size denoted l in blocks. All these blocks are elements of $GF(2^p)$. The

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systematic layout with parity vectors is achieved with the information dispersal matrix A , derived from an $m \times (m+k)$ Vander- monde matrix[7] :

$$\begin{matrix} 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ \beta_1 & \beta_2 & \dots & \beta_m & \beta_{m+1} & \dots & \beta_n \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \beta_{1m-1} & \beta_{2m-1} & \dots & \beta_{mm-1} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \beta_{m+1m-1} & \beta_{nm-1} & \dots & \dots \end{matrix}$$

where β_j ($j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$) are distinct elements randomly Picked from GF (2). After a series of basic row transformations, the preferred matrix A can be written as

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} I & P \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} P_{11} & P_{12} & \dots & P_{1k} & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ P_{21} & P_{22} & \dots & P_{2k} & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \\ P_{m1} & P_{m2} & \dots & P_{mk} & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

By multiplying F by A , the user obtains the encoded file: $G = F \cdot A = (G(1), G(2), \dots, G(m), G(m+1), \dots, G(n)) = (F_1, F_2, \dots, F_m, G(m+1), \dots, G(n))$, Where $G(j) = (g_1(j), g_2(j), \dots, g_l(j))^T$ ($j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$). noticed, the multiplication reproduces the original data file vectors of F and the remaining part $(G(m+1), \dots, G(n))$ are k parity vectors generated based on F .

Token pre-computation:

- Before file distribution the cloud clients pre-computes a certain number of short verification tokens on individual vector.
- Cloud client wants to make sure storage correctness for the data in the cloud; he challenges the cloud servers with a set of randomly generated block indices

Algorithm 1 *Token Pre_computation*

- 1: procedure
- 2: Choose parameters l, n and function f, φ ;
- 3: Choose the number t of tokens;
- 4: Choose the number r of index per confirmation;
- 5: produce master key K_{prp} and challenge key k_{chal} ;
- 6: **for** vector $G(j), j \leftarrow 1, n$ **do**
- 7: **for** round $i \leftarrow 1, t$ **d**
- 8: Derive $\alpha_i = f_{k_{chal}}(i)$ and k_{prp} from K_{prp}
- 9: compute
- 10 end for
- 11: end for
- 12: store all the vis locally

13: end procedure.

Correctness Verification and Error

Localization:

- Integrates the correctness verification and error localization (misbehaving server identification) using challenge response protocol.
- The response values from cloud servers for every challenge not only determine the correctness of the distributed storage but also contain information to locate potential data error(s).

The comparison between precomputed tokens and received response values can guarantee the identification of misbehaving server(s) when the data is corrupted.

The cloud client can reconstruct the original file by downloading the data vectors from the first m servers, assuming that they return the correct response values.

Algorithm 2 : Correctness Verification and Error Localization:

1: procedure CHALLENGE (i)

2: ecompute $\alpha_i = f_{kchal}(i)$ and k_{prp} from KPRP

3: Send $\{ \alpha_i, k(i)_{prp} \}$ to all the cloud server

4: Receive from servers: $\{ R_i(j) = \sum_{r=1}^m \alpha_i * G(j) [\varphi(i)(q)] \mid 1 \leq j \leq n \}$

5: $R(j) \leftarrow R(j) - \sum_{r=1}^m \alpha_i$

6: $f_{k_j}(s_{Iq,j}) \cdot \alpha_i$,

7: $I_q = \varphi_{k_{prp}(i)}(q)$

8: **end for**

9: if $((R_i(1), \dots, R_i(m)) \cdot P = (R_i(m+1), \dots, R_i(n)))$ then

10: Accept and ready for the next challenge.

10: else

11: for $(j \leftarrow 1, n)$ do

12: if $(R_i(j) \neq v_i(j))$ then

13: **return** server j is behaving.

14: **end if**, end for

15: end if

16: end procedure

V. CONCLUSION

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In this paper, we examine the problem of data security problem stored the in cloud data storage, which is mostly a distributed storage system. We relies on erasure-correcting code in the file distribution preparation to support redundancy parity vectors for verification of erasure coded data using the homomorphic token, In this paper our scheme achieves the integration of data error localization and storage correctness insurance. security analysis shows that our scheme is highly efficient and resilient to Byzantine failure, malicious data change attack, and even server colluding attacks.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Wang, Q. Wang, K. Ren, and W. Lou, "Ensuring data storage security in cloud computing," in Proc. of IWQoS'09, July 2009, pp.1-9
- [2] G. Ateniese, R. D. Pietro, L. V. Mancini, and G. Tsudik, "Scalable and Efficient Provable Data Possession," *Proc. Of SecureComm '08*, pp. 1- 10, 2008.
- [3] Amazon.com, "Amazon s3 availability event: July20,2008," Online at <http://status.aws.amazon.com/s3-20080720.html>, July 2008..
- [4] K. D. Bowers, A. Juels, and A. Oprea, "Hail: A high-availability and integrity layer for cloud storage," in *Proc. of CCS'09*, 2009, pp. 187-198.
- [5] A. Juels and J. Burton S. Kaliski, "Pors: Proofs of retrievability for large files," in *Proc. of CCS'07*, Alexandria, VA, October 2007, pp.584-597 [6] Sun Microsystems, Inc., "Building customer trust in cloud computing with transparent security," Online at <https://HYPERLINK> ""www.sun.com/offers/details/sun transparency.xml, November 2009.
- [7] Q. Wang, K. Ren, W. Lou, and Y. Zhang, "Dependable and secure sensor data storage with dynamic integrity assurance," in *Proc. Of IEEE INFOCOM'09*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, April 2009.
- [8] Q. Wang, K. Ren, W. Lou, and Y. Zhang, "Dependable and secure data storage with dynamic integrity assurance," in *Proc. Of IEEE INFOCOM'09*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, April 2009.
- [9] G. Ateniese, R. Burns, R. Curtmola, J. Herring, L. Kissinger, Z. Peterson, and D. Song, "Provable Data Possession at Untrusted Stores," *Proc. 14th ACM Conf. Computer and Comm. Security (CCS '07)*, pp. 598-609, Oct. 2007.
- [10] T. S. J. Schwarz and E. L. Miller, "Store, Forget, and Check: Using Algebraic Signatures to Check Remotely Administered Storage," *Proc. of ICDCS '06*, pp. 12-12, 2006.
- [11] J. Hendricks, G. Ganger, and M. Reiter, "Verifying Distributed Erasurecoded Data," *Proc. 26th ACM Symposium on Principles of Distributed Computing*, pp. 139-146, 2007.